

Formant Frequencies In Children With Normal Hearing And Profound Or Severe Hearing Impairments

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to discover the differences in vowel formant production (F1 and F2) in 33 children, aged 5-9 years, with a different hearing status (11 children with normal hearing (NH), 9 children with prelingual severe (SHI) (mean of hearing loss in dBHL, better ear=68,53, SD=18.90) and by 13 children with prelingual profound hearing impairment (PHI) (mean of hearing loss in dBHL, better ear=106.70, SD=4.82). Formant frequencies associated with 7 Slovenian vowels (/i/, closed /e/, open /e/, /a/, open /o/, closed /o/, /u/), produced during naming pictures or reading words from the Slovenian articulation test were obtained. All first formant and second formant frequencies of high front and back vowels of the speakers with hearing impairment were significantly different from those of the normal-hearing children. The findings suggest the role of the auditory feedback in vowel production in speakers with hearing impairment. The knowledge may be used in speech therapy in visual monitoring of vowel production in HI speakers and in acoustical engineering, to give more stress on high frequencies during acoustic processing.

Povzetek

Namen raziskave je analiza razlik v formantni produkciji (F1 in F2) 33 otrok, starih od 5 do 9 let, ki so polnočutni (11 otrok), naglušni (9 otrok, boljše uho=68,53, SD=18.90) ali gluhi (13 otrok, boljše uho=106.70, SD=4.82). Sedem samoglasnikov slovenskega jezika (polglasnik smo opustili) smo analizirali iz zvočnih posnetkov imenovanja ali branja besed artikulacijskega testa. Vsi prvi in drugi formanti sprednjih zgornjih ter zadnjih samoglasnikov otrok z izgubo sluha se statistično pomembno razlikujejo od formantov polnočutnih otrok. Rezultati opozarjajo na vlogo slušne povratne zanke za samoglasniško produkcijo. Podatke lahko uporabimo pri logopedski terapiji ob vidnem spremljanju samoglasniškega izgovora ter v zvočnih aplikacijah, ter opozarjajo na večje upoštevanje visokih frekvenc pri akustičnem procesiranju.

1. Introduction

Several authors claim that the speech production of individuals with severe prelingual hearing impairment is different from the speech of those with profound hearing impairment and from that of normal-hearing individuals, due to an inefficient auditory feedback (Murphy and Dodds, 2007, 248-250; Waldstein, 1990; Markides, 1983). The articulation manoeuvres for vowels are controlled through audition and through kinaesthesia (Nasir & Ostry, 2008; Nasin & Ostry; 2006, Purcell & Munhall, 2006). The indirect evidence of this statement can be drawn from results of several studies on formant production of deaf speakers (i.e. Waldstein, 1990; Nikolaidis & Sfakianaki, 2007).

Speakers with hearing impairment show less differentiated vowels and a more centralised vowel space. F1 and F2 formant frequencies show reduced ranges during the production of the different vowel qualities, and there can be an extensive overlap of vowel areas and a tendency toward the neutral schwa (Angelocci, Kopp & Holbrook, 1964; Ryalls, Larouche & Giroux, 1983; Fletcher, 1995). This reduced differentiation of vowels has been attributed to limited auditory feedback and the relative invisibility of articulatory gestures needed for vowel production (Monsen, 1976). Higher frequencies tend to be more

affected, as hearing sensitivity is greatly reduced above 1000 Hz for individuals with hearing impairment. As a result, more errors have generally been reported for the high and the middle vowels compared to the low ones and for the front than the back vowels. The high frequency, low intensity F2 formants of the high vowels are more likely to be affected than the lower-frequency, more intense F2 formants of the back vowels (Nicolaidis & Sfakiannaki, 2007). Taking into account the fact that residual hearing most often covers low frequencies better than high ones, this is an indirect proof that vowels are controlled by the auditory feedback most. In Subtelny, Whitehead and Samar's report on the speech production of four deaf women, the formant structure disclosed consistent neutralisation of vowels, with F2 values clustering in the 1500–2100 Hz frequency range, which is attributed to the observed restricted horizontal movements of the tongue within the oral and pharyngeal cavities. If these restrictions affect the production of all vowels, a lower F2 might be assumed for the front vowels, which normally have a high F2. A higher F2 frequency would be anticipated for back vowels, which normally have a low F2 (Subtelny, Whitehead, Samar 1992, 574-579). Schenk, Baumgartner, and Hamzavi (2003) analyzed the frequencies of the first and second formants and the vowel spaces of selected vowels in word-in-context

condition of 23 postlingually deafened and 18 normal-hearing speakers were compared. All first formant frequencies (F1) of the postlingually deafened speakers were significantly different from those of the normal-hearing people. The values of F1 were higher for the vowels /e/ (418±61 Hz compared with 359±52 Hz, $P=0.006$) and /o/ (459±58 compared with 390±45 Hz, $P=0.0003$) and lower for /a/ (765±115 Hz compared with 851±146 Hz, $P=0.038$). The second formant frequency (F2) only showed a significant increase for the vowel /e/ (2016±347 Hz compared with 2279±250 Hz, $P=0.012$). The results of Waldstein (1990) exploring selected properties of consonants, vowels, and suprasegmentals in the speech of seven totally postlingually deafened individuals demonstrates that all deafened subjects showed a reduction in formant frequency ranges and in the acoustic vowel space. The reduced range values suggest a smaller degree of tongue movement in articulation. Waldstein reports an increased variability of formant frequencies for both F1 and F2.

2. Goal of the paper

The purpose of this study was to find out the differences in vowel formant production between children with normal hearing and those children with prelingual profound and severe hearing impairment. The hypotheses were:

H1: The F2 values of anterior vowels are lower and F2 formant values of the posterior vowels are higher in the hearing-impaired groups, according to the degree of hearing impairment, compared with the values of normal-hearing individuals.

H2: The ranges of F1 from high to low vowels and of F2 from anterior to posterior vowels are smaller in the hearing impaired groups, according to the degree of hearing impairment, compared with the values of normal-hearing children.

H3: The formant space in the F2-F1 plane is the smallest in children with profound hearing impairment, followed by children with severe hearing impairment and the greatest formant space in the F2-F1 plane is in normal-hearing children.

3. Materials and methods

Participants: The experimental group¹: twenty-two Slovenian children from 5 to 9 years old² with profound (13) or severe (9) hearing impairment were included in the study (severe hearing impairment: 5 males, 4 females, mean of age=7.6 years SD=1,51; profound hearing impairment: 8 males, 5 females, mean of age=7.7 years SD=1.32). All presented severe and profound sensorineural prelingual deafness in unaided condition (Table 1). All were children from non-inclusive kindergartens and schools for the deaf and hard of hearing in centres for speech and language

impairments in Ljubljana, Maribor and Portorož in Slovenia. This means that they were sign language users in the deaf community and were orally trained for communication with those who don't use sign language and for bilingual education (Slovenian sign language and Slovenian oral language). All of them were detected and diagnosed in early childhood during neonatology screening tests or up to the 3 years of age. All of the children were fitted with analogue behind-the-ear hearing aids and did not have any developmental disorders. Three had deaf parents. None were cochlear implant users. All the speakers used the hearing aid continuously (often or always during the day), mainly during the educational process, which was bilingual and bimodal, i.e. Slovenian and/or sign language. The school curriculum requires to use both oral Slovenian and sign language (production and perception).

The control group: Eleven Slovenian normal-hearing children (7 males, 4 females) aged from 5 to 9 (M=7.0 years, SD=1.18) were included in the study as the control group. None of the normal-hearing children had any developmental diseases or disorders.

According to the Welch robust test of equality of means, the experimental and control groups were not statistically different in age ($p=0.401$); the Chi square test shows that also the differences in the distribution of gender were not statistically relevant ($p=0.931$).

	N	Mean	SD	SE	Min	Max
Mean of hearing loss in dBHL, right ear						
SHI	9	77.91	22.10	7.37	48.27	103.73
PHI	13	109.72	4.57	1.27	104.36	119.09
Mean of hearing loss in dBHL, left ear						
SHI	9	71.83	17.27	5.76	45.91	91.82
PHI	13	109.32	7.49	2.08	98.64	124.55
Mean of hearing loss in dBHL, better ear						
SHI	9	68.53	18.90	6.30	45.91	90.00
PHI	13	106.70	4.82	1.33	98.64	114.09
Mean of hearing loss in dBHL, worse ear						
SHI	9	81.21	18.97	6.32	49.27	103.73
PHI	13	112.29	6.11	1.70	105.14	124.55

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the mean values of hearing loss for better and worse ear, and for right and left ear (NH=normal hearing, SHI=severe hearing impairment, PHI=profound hearing impairment)

Variables: age, degree of hearing loss (mean of hearing loss in dBHL for right and left ear and for better and worse ear), F1 and F2 formant frequency values for seven vowels (/i/, closed /e/, open /e/, /a/, open /o/, closed /o/, open /o/ and /u/) of Slovenian language (Cronbach's alpha: 0.972). The schwa is omitted due to frequent omission or substitution with closed /e/ or open /e/ in the speech of deaf subjects.

Data acquisition: The Three-position test of articulation for Slovenian (Globačnik, 1999) and an additional list of seven words were used. The test battery of articulation, used by all speech and language therapists in Slovenia, is a set of well-known, frequent words with simple and complex phoneme structures. In the set of the elicited words the most frequent stressed

¹ The research was made in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (1983).

² The beginning of the mutation can be fixed at the age of 10–11 years, according to Hacki, Heitmüller (1999).

syllables were the initial syllables. The most frequent stressed syllable structure was CV.

Analysis tools: The speech of all participants was recorded on a Sony TCD-D8 DAT recorder with a Sennheiser MD 441 U microphone, which has an even frequency response from 0 to 20 kHz. The recordings were monitored on-line by the investigator by visual inspection of the VU meter on the tape recorder. The recordings were sampled at 16 KHz and digitized using a HP notebook. The data were stored with CoolEdit2000 software for sound data processing and analysed with tools for speech analysis (Praat version 5.1.40 and SpeechAnalyzer SIL version 3.0.1). The fundamental and first and second formants were taken from the most stable portion of the vowel in stressed syllables. Typically this was the midpoint of the vowel. If the centre portion of the vowel did not yield the most stable spectra, measurements were taken slightly earlier or later than the midpoint. Formants were selected by way of convergence among values derived from spectrographic displays and FFT first, assisted by LPC analyses in both software packages. First approximations for formant frequencies were provided by spectrographic display and FFT analysis, with supportive measurements obtained from LPC analysis. We analysed from min 2 (open /e/) to 33 instances per vowel for each speaker. The statistical analysis was performed with WASP 18.0 for Windows.

Statistical analysis: frequency analysis was used to describe the frequencies of the variables, the distribution and to test the hypothesis H2 and H3, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to test the normal distribution (all variables are normal distributed at $p < 0.05$); ANOVA, Welch analysis and post-hoc Bonferroni analysis were used to test the hypothesis H1 and H2 and to analyse the statistically relevant differences between formant values (means) in children with normal hearing, and those with severe and profound hearing impairment.

3. Results

The results show some differences in vowel production between the three groups (Table 2, Figure 1). The mean F1 values show a shifted vertical space, with frequency mean range of 620/590 – 991 Hz for the children with severe hearing impairment and a vowel space with frequency range of 639/662 – 1007 Hz in children with profound hearing impairment, compared to that of the children with normal hearing and a frequency range of 532/551 – 879 Hz.

Comparisons of the second formants of the vowels produced by the children with PHI and SHI revealed neutralisation of vowels, with F2 values clustering in the 1104 – 2509 Hz frequency range for severe impairment and in the 1222 – 2494 Hz frequency range for PHI (in subjects with NH, F2 values cluster in the 975 – 2910 Hz frequency range), which is attributed to the restricted horizontal movements of the tongue within the oral and pharyngeal cavities, according to Subtenly, Whitehead, Samar (1992, 574-579) and Engwall (1999).

		N	Mean	SD	Min	Max.
/i/ f1	NH	11	532	40.55	467	583
	SHI	9	620	73.22	483	719
	PHI	13	662	90.32	503	883
/i/ f2	NH	11	2910	334.97	2410	3493
	SHI	9	2509	267.10	2127	2853
	PHI	13	2494	306.58	1981	2932
Closed /e/ f1	NH	11	536	56.18	455	655
	SHI	9	627	100.23	507	798
	PHI	13	652	142.50	431	1005
Closed /e/ f2	NH	11	2686	267.25	2398	3352
	SHI	9	2359	205.17	2047	2632
	PHI	13	2120	464.70	815	2612
Open /e/ f1	NH	11	738	158.07	519	1065
	SHI	9	692	133.68	464	867
	PHI	13	736	204.04	497	1153
Open /e/ f2	NH	31	2400	201.57	2174	2812
	SHI	14	2267	219.41	1968	2553
	PHI	25	2152	345.83	1338	2732
/a/ f1	NH	32	879	126.12	719	1051
	SHI	14	991	76.20	882	1095
	PHI	25	1007	148.69	784	1293
/a/ f2	NH	11	1572	209.49	1143	1828
	SHI	9	1727	152.92	1506	2001
	PHI	13	1754	198.81	1457	2006
Open /o/ f1	NH	11	608	118.49	494	824
	SHI	9	799	130.99	671	1078
	PHI	13	793	134.19	628	1052
Open /o/ f2	NH	11	1206	121.20	1040	1425
	SHI	9	1448	113.29	1298	1686
	PHI	13	1535	207.99	1253	1783
Closed /o/ f1	NH	11	554	52.55	503	684
	SHI	9	670	81.52	570	841
	PHI	13	691	123.36	459	941
Closed /o/ f2	NH	11	1110	88.40	976	1255
	SHI	9	1301	112.47	1163	1527
	PHI	13	1348	222.14	982	1813
/u/ f1	NH	32	551	38.90	492	614
	SHI	14	590	65.58	491	675
	PHI	25	639	115.99	434	808
/u/ f2	NH	32	975	115.87	744	1095
	SHI	14	1104	136.24	881	1243
	PHI	25	1222	141.81	1060	1556

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the formant values (in Hertz) for the Slovenian vowels in children with normal hearing (NH), severe (SHI) and profound hearing loss (PHI)

		N	Mean	SD
d_i_f1	NH	11	.06	40.55
	SHI	9	-87.75	73.22
	PHI	13	-130.49	90.32
d_i_f2	NH	11	-.45	334.97
	SHI	9	400.96	267.10
	PHI	13	416.39	306.58
d_closed_e_f1	NH	11	.39	56.18
	SHI	9	-90.85	100.23
	PHI	13	-115.80	142.50
d_closed_e_f2	NH	11	.47	267.25
	SHI	9	326.82	205.17
	PHI	13	566.07	464.70
D_open_e_f1	NH	10	.17	158.07
	SHI	9	45.54	133.68
	PHI	13	1.63	204.04
d_open_e_f2	NH	10	-.17	201.57
	SHI	9	132.94	219.41
	PHI	13	248.17	345.83
d_a_f1	NH	11	.1250	126.12
	SHI	9	-111.94	76.20
	PHI	13	-127.76	148.69
d_a_f2	NH	11	.13	209.49
	SHI	9	-155.37	152.92
	PHI	13	-181.58	198.81
d_open_o_f1	NH	11	.40	118.49
	SHI	9	-191.00	130.99
	PHI	13	-185.00	134.19
d_open_o_f2	NH	11	.16	121.20
	SHI	9	-242.18	113.29
	PHI	13	-329.26	207.99
D_closed_o_f1	NH	11	-.02	52.55
	SHI	9	-116.23	81.52
	PHI	13	-136.74	123.36
d_closed_o_f2	NH	10	-.41	88.40
	SHI	9	-190.73	112.47
	PHI	13	-238.15	222.14
d_u_f1	NH	10	.25	38.90
	SHI	9	-38.52	65.58
	PHI	13	-88.39	115.99
d_u_f2	NH	11	.3977	115.87
	SHI	9	-129.05	136.24
	PHI	13	-246.54	141.81

Table 3: Descriptives of the deviation among SHI and PHI speakers in formant frequency (Hertz) from the standard formant value as derived from the control group data set (NH)

Generally, the means of F1 are usually slightly higher in the anterior and posterior vowels in the PHI compared with formant values of those with SHI; with the SHI group the means of F2 are usually higher in the anterior vowels and lower in the posterior vowels compared to the PHI. Compared with formant values of the children with NH, a lower F2 might be assumed in children with PHI and SHI for the front vowels, which normally have a high F2, and a higher F2 frequency

would be produced for the back vowels, which normally have a low F2. The F1 values are normally higher for the front and the back vowels with children with both PHI and SHI (except F1 of open /e/ where the speakers with SHI have lower F1 than PHI and NH speakers).

Figure 1: Vowel production: F1 and F2 in of NH, SHI and PHI children

Figure 2: Vowel production in F2 – F1 plane of NH, SHI and PHI children

Figure 3: The deviation among SHI and PHI speakers in formant frequency from the standard formant value as derived from the control group data set (NH)

Test of homogeneity of variances				
Vowel / formant	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Open /o/ f2	6.370	2	28	.005*
/u/ f1	5.168	2	30	.012*
Welch Robust Tests of Equality of Means				
/i/ f1	13.196	2	17.092	.000*
/i/ f2	5.804	2	19.291	.011*
Closed /e/ f1	5.411	2	16.967	.015*
Closed /e/ f2	8.150	2	19.925	.003*
Open /o/ f1	7.207	2	17.605	.005*

Open /o/ f2	13.995	2	18.607	.000*
Closed /o/ f1	10.656	2	17.666	.001*
Closed /o/ f2	11.678	2	18.499	.001*
/u/ f1	3,868	2	17,016	,041*
/u/ f2	10,715	2	18,850	,001*

Table 4: Test of homogeneity of variances and Welch Robust Tests of Equality of Means

(I) hearing status	(J) hearing Status	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Dependent Variable /i/ f1				
NH	SHI	-87.8063*	32.53751	.034
	PHI	-130.5462*	29.65682	.000
Dependent Variable /i/ f2				
NH	SHI	401.4079*	137.81961	.020
	PHI	416.8406*	125.61781	.007
Dependent Variable closed /e/ f1				
NH	PHI	-116.1948*	44.60315	.042
Dependent Variable closed /e/ f2				
NH	PHI	565.6009*	142.74826	.001
Dependent Variable open /o/ f1				
NH	SHI	-191.3882*	60.79372	.012
	PHI	-185.3900*	55.92209	.008
Dependent Variable open /o/ f2				
NH	SHI	-242.3359*	76.60001	.011
	PHI	-329.4118*	70.46176	.000
Dependent Variable closed /o/ f1				
NH	SHI	-116.2069*	42.11623	.029
	PHI	-136.7210*	38.38748	.004
Dependent Variable closed /o/ f2				
NH	SHI	-190.3168*	72.07830	.039
	PHI	-237.7365*	65.69688	.003
Dependent Variable /u/ f1				
NH	PHI	-88.6045*	34.35591	.045
Dependent Variable /u/ f2				
NH	PHI	-246.9376*	54.14627	.000

Table 5: Multiple Comparisons - Bonferroni post hoc analysis of vowel formant variables between children with NH, with SHI and PHI (* The mean difference is significant at the .05 level)

According to the hypothesis H2, we can state that NH speakers show a larger range in F2 formant production from anterior to posterior vowels (2910 Hz-975 Hz=1935 Hz) in comparison with speech production in children with SHI (2509 Hz-1104 Hz=1405 Hz) and PHI (2494 Hz-1222 Hz=1272 Hz). In the F1 formant production of high and low vowels, NH speakers show higher F1 values (532/551 Hz-879 Hz=347/328 Hz) in comparison with the vowel production in children with PHI (662/639 Hz-1007 Hz=368/445 Hz) and those with SHI (620/590 Hz-991 Hz=401/371 Hz). As a result, ranges in NH speakers are larger than in SHI and PHI speakers.

Comparing the children with profound and severe hearing impairment, generally, there are smaller standard deviations in the severe hearing impairment group and greater standard deviations in the profound hearing impairment group. In the children with profound and severe hearing impairment the standard

deviations in some variables (i.e. F1 of /i/, closed and open /e/, open and closed /o/, /u/ and F2 of open /e/ and /o/, closed /o/ and /u/) are much greater than in those with normal hearing; the highest standard deviation is found in the group with profound hearing impairment.

From Figures 1 and 2, it is clear that the formant space (F1-F2 scatterplot) with profound hearing impairment is smaller than that with severe impairment and that the space in SHI children is smaller than that in the NH children. The greatest differences are in the anterior vowel production: normal-hearing children differentiate the three anterior vowels much better than those with severe and profound hearing impairment, especially the closed and open /e/. The greatest differences are between children with normal hearing and children with profound hearing impairment, especially in the second formant values (Table 2).

To clarify the differences we computed the deviations among speakers with SHI and PHI in formant frequency from the standard formant values as derived from the control group data set (NH speakers). Table 3 shows the greatest deviation in PHI speakers for all formant values, except in F1 of open /e/ and open /o/. These two vowels are influenced by the dialect spoken by speakers, and they are very variable. Considering that open /e/ and open /o/ are more visible than front and back vowels and more open, the speakers with PHI may use more visible feedback than the speakers with SHI. The Figure 3 is very informative: all the formant values in speakers with SHI and PHI deviate from the control group data set. Greater deviations are visible in speakers with PHI, comparing with those of SHI speakers; more detailed, the anterior F2 values are lower in frequency and the difference is positive, whereas the F2 of back vowels and the F1 values of all vowels are higher and the difference is negative.

As the degree of hearing loss increased the deviation in frequency from the standard second formant values of the front values, as derived from the control group data set, increased (positive values) and the values of the F2 were lower than those in the control group data set; the deviation in the back values decreased, the first formants increased in the extreme back and front vowels and decreased in the middle-low vowel.

Simultaneously comparing the means of the three groups (Table 4) yielded the results that at $p < .05$ all the variables except F1 of /u/ and F2 of open /o/ are homogeneous in variance. As seen in Table 4, all the variables of high front and back rounded vowels, except F1 and F2 of /a/ and open /e/ did not pass the robust test of equality of means (Welch method, $p < .05$). The greatest differences in the second formant are for the anterior high vowel /i/ and for the back high rounded vowel open /o/, and the greatest differences in first formant values are for the back high rounded vowels open /o/ and closed /o/.

The results of analysing the differences between the three pairs of groups (NH – SHI, NH – PHI, SHI – PHI) in the Bonferroni post-hoc analysis, the values in Table 5 show that the only formant values that are consistent between the three groups, are the first and second

formants of the vowels /a/ and open /e/, the most central vowels, where the auditory control is minimal: the only movement required is a jaw vertical movement with minimal tongue movement.

According to the results, we can accept the first, second and third hypotheses in their entirety. The F2 values are more at risk for neutralisation / clustering / overlapping than F1 values. In addition to the generally reduced perception of F2 formants, tongue placement along the front-back axis in the oral cavity is difficult to perceive visually. On the other hand, better residual hearing in the region of F1 frequencies and relatively better visibility of tongue height associated with jaw displacement, which can be accessible in speech reading, makes variation in F1 more prominent (Nicolaidis & Sfakiannaki, 2007). Comparing our speakers and formant values, and the conclusions of the cited research, we can say that there is a general belief that the formant space in speakers with hearing impairment is reduced, the F2 line inverted, and F2 values clustered. Comparing to the results of Subtenly et al. (1992), with F2 frequency range 1500-2100 Hz, in our analysis F2 values clustered from 2509 Hz to 1727 Hz. Shizuo and Ryuzemon (1957) reported that [i] and [o] in speakers with hearing impairment, aged 6-11 years, deviated most from the production in NH speakers. In our research great deviations were in /i/ and (closed and open) /o/ and in closed /e/ and /u/. Schenk, Baumgartner and Hamzavi (2003) showed differences in all F1 values and differences in F2 in [e] only. Our study – comparing NH and HI groups - found differences in all high front and back vowels (in F1 and F2). Only open /e/ and /a/ didn't differ in the three groups. It is important to underline that Slovenian language has 13 stressed vowels (7 long and 6 short) and 6 unstressed short ones; a direct comparison with other languages with other vowel systems is consequently inappropriate. We may compare the rules of vowel neutralisation, clustering or overlapping, the tendencies of range reduction. We can say that our study and the cited ones are similar.

The presented findings might have an impact to the language teaching process for the children with hearing disabilities: they offer to speech and language therapists the norms of formant production and encourage the use of audio-video feedback tools for speech production monitoring to widen the formant production space.

Future studies should examine the F2/F1 ratios in vowel production in NH, SHI and PHI group in order to understand the similarities between speakers and groups and to compare these ratios with ratios of older speakers (adult males and females).

4. References

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